

LEAN IN THE PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY: REVIEW OF KEY STUDIES

PRIMENA LIN PRISTUPA U FARMACEUTSKOJ INDUSTRIJI: PREGLED KLJUČNIH RADOVA

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Abstract: Building upon a previously published bibliometric analysis, this paper explores how Lean methodology has been applied in the pharmaceutical industry through a review of the most cited studies. The findings show that while Lean demonstrates strong potential for improving efficiency and performance, its implementation remains limited and not yet fully integrated across organizations.

Keywords: Lean, Pharmaceutical industry, Literature review

Apstrakt: Nadovezujući se na prethodno objavljenu bibliometrijsku analizu literature, ovaj rad istražuje primenu lin pristupa u farmaceutskoj industriji kroz pregled najcitiranijih studija. Rezultati pokazuju da lin ima značajan potencijal za unapređenje efikasnosti i performansi, ali njegova primena i dalje ostaje ograničena i nije u potpunosti integrisana u organizacione procese.

Ključne reči: Lin, Farmaceutska industrija, Pregled literature

1. INTRODUCTION

The pharmaceutical industry faces challenges such as stringent regulatory demands, high research and development costs, outdated production technologies, and complex supply chains, that can lead to greater risks and inefficiencies (Moosivand et al., 2019; Sarkis et al., 2021). These pressures force companies to reduce costs while still ensuring quality and compliance. Lean methodology helped with these type of problems by focusing on waste reduction (Purushothaman et al., 2020), process efficiency (Gutierrez et al., 2022), and better resource utilization (Cai & Freiheit, 2014). Because of this, it is important to explore how Lean principles are applied in the pharmaceutical industry and to what extent they contribute to overcoming these challenges.

Lean has been widely studied and put into practice in many different industries, but the impact on the pharmaceutical sector hasn't been explored as much (Gatić et al., 2025).

For this reason, a two-part literature review was conducted to examine the existing body of literature. A bibliometric analysis (Gatić et al., 2025) was carried out to identify relevant studies and trends in the field. Building upon that, this paper will present a structured overview of the selected papers. To gain a better understanding of how Lean is implemented within pharmaceutical companies, it is necessary to go beyond citation metrics from bibliometric analysis and examine the content of research papers. Since the bibliometric analysis alone could not provide detailed insights into how Lean is implemented within companies, the next phase of the research focused on the analysis of the most cited studies.

2. METHODOLOGY

Considering the challenges that the pharmaceutical industry faces, the success of Lean implementation in other sectors, and the growing use of it in process industries, it was necessary to examine the extent to which Lean has been studied and applied in the pharmaceutical sector. To achieve this, after a bibliometric analysis (Gatić et al., 2025), a structured literature review was conducted, following the recommendation of Denyer & Tranfield (2009).

The Scopus database was used to conduct the research. Only peer-reviewed journal articles in English were taken into consideration, while books, conference papers, and non-business-oriented studies were excluded. The final database included 101 studies following multiple iterations of exclusions.

The Pareto principle was used to determine which contributions had the greatest impact after the final sample was collected. Inspired by the methodological approach of Bajaj et al. (2018) this study applied the Pareto principle to the literature review, focusing on the top 20% of the most cited papers in the field. This allowed for the study to concentrate on the most significant contributions found in the literature. The primary selection criterion was the number of citations. The study with the most citations at the time of data collection from Scopus had 82, while the study with the fewest citations had only 16.

3. RESULTS

The top five studies had more than 40 citations each, while the bottom five had fewer than 25. The distribution of the publications through time is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Distribution of studies by year of publication

As shown in Figure 1, a noticeable increase occurred in 2019, when four studies were published, coinciding with the overall rise in Lean-related research within the pharmaceutical sector (Gatić et al., 2025). In most other years, only one or two studies were published, while in 2012, 2013, 2017, and 2020, none of the top 20 most cited papers appeared. As Table 1 shows, the majority of papers (65%) represent empirical research.

Table 1: Categories of analyzed studies

Category	Number of papers	Share [%]
Case study	3	15
Survey	5	25
Action research	5	25
Modelling	1	5
Simulation	1	5
Literature review	5	25

Action research, surveys, and literature reviews were the most common approaches, each accounting for one-quarter of the sample. Table 2 highlights the studies that explicitly describe how Lean was applied in the pharmaceutical industry or the results that were achieved.

Table 2 provides insight that Value Stream Mapping (VSM) and Kanban were the most frequently applied tools (Table 2). Interestingly, two studies addressed packaging-related issues, while another dealt with tablet manufacturing. Except for the papers focusing on overall business processes, most studies examined areas outside direct production.

Table 2: Studies, methods, tools, and techniques

Study	Research method	Tools and techniques	Business area
Abideen & Mohamad, (2021)	Simulation	VSM, Kanban, JIT, Heijunka, 5S	Distribution /Warehousing
Bevilacqua et al., (2015)	Action research	SIPOC, Flowchart, 5S, Kanban, SMED, TPM, Spagetti diagram	Packaging
Byrne et al., (2021)	Action research	VSM, Ishikawa diagram, A3, 5 Whys	Tablet production
(Papalexi et al., 2016)	Action research	Kanban	Warehousing
(Cogdill et al., 2007)	Case study	Lean methods combined with Process analytical technologies	Overall business
(Chowdary & George, 2011)	Case study/ Action research	5 Whys, VSM	Packaging
(Nenni et al., 2014)	Case study	Kanban-CONWIP system	Manufacturing process

The findings of individual studies show the significant impact Lean practices have. Abideen & Mohamad (2021) focusing on distribution, used simulation with Kanban, JIT, and Heijunka, and predicted reductions in lead time by 51.43% and in overall process time by 44.41%, at the same time, the value-added time percentage increased by 70,6 % and the non-value-added percentage decreased by 52%. Bevilacqua et al. (2015) and Chowdary & George (2011) both papers addressed medicine packaging. Both studies reported great improvement after implementing Lean. Bevilacqua et al. (2015) reported reductions in changeover time by 61.5%, cycle time by 64.1%, and Chowdary & George (2011) reported the need for 50% less workforce. Byrne et al. (2021) highlighted packaging as a bottleneck and reported savings of nearly half a million dollars after improvements. Papalexi et al. (2016) demonstrated a potential 71.8% reduction in storage costs through Kanban, they also noted challenges with short shelf-life medicines. Nenni et al. (2014) reduced in-process inventories by 37% after 90 days of applying a Kanban-CONWIP system.

In their survey research Cook et al., (2014) showed that academics, industry professionals, and regulatory bodies all agree that using Quality by Design (QbD), can help get better results and make Lean production lines work better and at the same time, it is good for the patient. Friedli et al. (2010) conducted a longitudinal study and documented significant increases in Overall Equipment Effectiveness and preventive maintenance attributed to Just in Time and Total Quality Management. Garza-Reyes et al. (2018) looked into the European pharmaceutical industry and found limited readiness for Lean, citing compliance with good manufacturing practices (GMP) were more important than operational excellence.

Research conducted in developing regions, such as Alkunsol et al. (2019) survey of 120 managers in Jordan, highlighted the importance of waste reduction by types and its impact on productivity and profitability. Ullman & Boutellier (2008) identified two distinct cultures in the pharmaceutical sector, innovation and production, arguing that Lean is more applicable to production. Other theoretical contributions, including Venugopal & Saleeshya (2019), highlighted unused human potential as a hidden waste, proposing integration of Lean and agile practices for sustainability. Gebauer et al. (2009) suggested that research-driven companies are less likely to adopt Lean, while Carleysmith et al., (2009) demonstrated that Lean can also be applied in pharmaceutical R&D, especially in laboratory routines, and is compatible with GMP practices.

4. DISCUSSION

To the search date (December 2022), only 101 studies have been published specifically on Lean in the pharmaceutical sector, while a simple Web of Science search for *Lean Manufacturing* (October 2025) returned more than 7,500 results. Most of the identified papers are published in journals targeted at pharmaceutical audiences, rather than in outlets oriented toward broader business and management (Gatić et al., 2025). On top of that, there is no established network of authors working consistently in this field, which limits both collaboration and in-depth exploration (Gatić et al., 2025). Over time, no significant thematic shifts have been observed (Gatić et al., 2025).

It is also interesting that only one paper out of 101 was authored by Serbian researchers, and that the broader region of Southeast Europe is also largely not present, although there are many strong pharmaceutical companies in Serbia and the region. Likewise, research addressing the application of Lean in the pharmaceutical industries of developing countries is almost entirely lacking. However, when digging deeper than just bibliometric metrics, this research shows that Lean can be implemented in the pharmaceutical industry successfully. This is aligned with research being done in other process industries, such as the petrochemical industry (Barsegyan, 2020) or paper manufacturing (Adeodu et al., 2021). However, this review showed that the focus remains on operational improvements rather than comprehensive business transformation into a Lean organization. While some studies reported results at the organizational level, these were still achieved through the application of Lean at the operational level rather than through full-scale Lean transformation.

This review provides strong evidence of the benefits of Lean implementation in the pharmaceutical industry. For example, Haleem et al. (2015) reported that AstraZeneca, by introducing pull principles in 2002, reduced lead time by 25% during a 30% increase in demand for a product generating over USD 1.5 billion annually. Other studies demonstrated inventory reductions of 37% (Nenni et al., 2014), 56.8% fewer finished goods stocks (Papalexi et al., 2016) a 38% reduction in workspace requirements, and a 50% reduction in workforce needs (Chowdary & George, 2011). Cogdill et al. (2007)

estimated that by implementing Lean practices to lower the inventory of the raw material, work in progress, and finished goods, annual operational cost savings could exceed USD 13 million. Similarly, Alkunsol et al. (2019) reported that Lean Six Sigma can reduce defects in pmanufacturing.

Previous research points out certian downsides. Although Lean has the potential to deliver improvements at the strategic as well as operational level, relatively few studies have studied its systematic application or on the tools that might enable such outcomes, leading to the barriers of adoption (Dixit et al., 2019). Research-driven companies, where tend to deprioritize Lean (Gebauer et al., 2009). Companies often lack awareness of Lean and Green operations, and the pharmaceutical sector has been underexplored in this regard (Singh et al., 2016). Even in developed European countries, Lean research remains limited, and pharmaceutical firms are not strongly committed to enhancing production processes through Lean (Garza-Reyes et al., 2018).

When it comes to Lean tools and techniques, only a small number of studies explicitly identified the tools used. Among these, Value Stream Mapping and Kanban emerged as the most frequently applied methods. The 5 Whys tool was also commonly used for root-cause analysis. While VSM and Kanban were used to achieve measurable improvements, Friedli et al. (2010) observed that these tools are still not widely adopted in pharmaceutical manufacturing.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this review shows that Lean has a strong potential for implementation in the pharmaceutical industry. Still, most existing studies focus on support processes rather than core operations, and address specific aspects rather than providing a holistic view of organizational transformation.

This literature review is not without limitations. The search was done in December 2022 and only looked at journal articles that were indexed in Scopus. The qualitative analysis was limited to 20 out of the 101 studies. The qualitative analysis was limited to 20 of the 101 studies identified in the final dataset. Future research should include broader literature and empirical studies so that the implementation of Lean in the pharmaceutical industry could be better understood.

LITERATURE

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